

The use of N- α -Pyridyl-N'-Benzoyl Thiourea as a Selective Reagent for Palladium

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N- α -Pyridyl-N'-benzoyl thiourea has been successfully employed in the determination of palladium by both gravimetry and spectrophotometry. The organic reagent forms a deep brown precipitate with palladium(II) at room temperature in the range of acidity from 1.6(N) to 0.08(N) with respect to hydrochloric acid, which can be weighed as Pd(C₁₃H₉N₃OS). Using proper masking agents the metal has been determined by the organic precipitant in the presence of almost all of the base metals and noble metals except platinum. The deep brown complex is extracted quantitatively in the pH range 1.4 to 4.6 with a mixture of chloroform and ethanol for the spectrophotometric determination of the metal. The extract shows maximum absorbance at 346 nm, obeys Beer's law at 350 nm over the range of concentration of the metal from 1.18 μ g/ml to 9.44 μ g/ml. Palladium has been spectrophotometrically determined with the chelating agent in the presence of all of the base metals and noble metals.

ORGANIC reagents for the gravimetric and spectrophotometric determinations of palladium are quite large in number, but most of them are not specific for the determination of the metal. Some of the thioligands proposed for the determination of palladium are: Thionalide^{1,2}, bismuthiol I and bismuthiol II^{3,4}, 2-mercaptobenzothiazole and 2-mercaptobenzimidazole⁵, thiophenol, thiobarbituric acid, phenyl thiohydantoic acid⁶, thiosalicylic acid⁷, diphenyldithiophosphoric acid⁸ and thiosalicylamide⁹.

In an earlier communication Shome and coworkers¹⁰ reported a qualitative study of the reactions of N- α -pyridyl-N'-benzoyl thiourea (PBT) with the platinum metals. The present investigation deals with the analytical applications of the reagent in the gravimetric as well as spectrophotometric determination of palladium. The metal is quantitatively precipitated as a deep brown complex with PBT in 1.6 (N) to 0.08(N) hydrochloric acid medium and the precipitate can be weighed as Pd(C₁₃H₉N₃OS.) The deep brown palladium-PBT complex is quantitatively extracted with a mixture of chloroform and ethanol in the pH range 1.4-4.6 for the spectrophotometric determination of the metal. Palladium is determined by both gravimetry and spectrophotometry with the organic reagent in the presence of large amounts of almost all of the base metals and noble metals. Platinum (II and IV), however interferes with the gravimetric determination of palladium with PBT.

Experimental

Apparatus, Reagents and Chemicals: A Carl Zeiss spectrophotometer, PM Q II model, with

1cm quartz cells was employed for transmittance measurements. All the pH measurements were carried out with a Cambridge pH meter (Bench model).

Palladium chloride (E. Merck) was dissolved in dilute hydrochloric acid and the solution was standardised by the dimethyl glyoxime method. Solutions for the spectrophotometric determination were prepared by dilution of the stock solution with distilled water. Diverse ion solutions were prepared by dissolving separately weighed amounts of the corresponding salts in distilled water or in dilute hydrochloric acid.

A 1% (W/V) ethanolic solution of N- α -pyridyl-N'-benzoyl thiourea (PBT) was employed for the precipitation of palladium. For spectrophotometric measurements a 0.01(M) ethanolic solution of the reagent was used.

All the reagents used were of A. R. grade.

Properties and composition of the complex: The Pd-PBT complex is deep brown in colour, stable towards heat, light and air and slowly decomposes at 158°. The complex was analysed to determine the percentage of palladium, nitrogen and sulphur present in it. The analytical results are as follows:

Percentage found: Pd=29.40, N=11.55, S=8.92.

Percentage required for Pd (C₁₃H₉N₃OS)

Pd=29.50 N=11.60, S=8.85.

Gravimetric Determination of Palladium. :

Procedure: A measured amount of standard palladium solution was diluted to 150 ml in a beaker and the acidity was adjusted to 1.5(N)-0.1(N) with hydrochloric acid. The solution was heated to 70°-80° and the PBT solution (3-4 times the theoretical amount) was added and stirred. The deep brown precipitate formed, was digested on a hot water bath for one hour with occasional stirring, filtered through a sintered glass crucible and washed with hot 1% hydrochloric acid. The complex was dried at 110°-115°, cooled in a desiccator and weighed as Pd (C₁₃H₉N₃OS). The results are shown in Table-1.

TABLE-1 DETERMINATION OF PALLADIUM BY WEIGHING THE Pd-PBT COMPLEX

Palladium taken mg.	Palladium found mg.	Error mg.	Palladium taken mg.	Palladium found mg.	Error mg.
5.82	5.79	-0.03	17.46	17.46	± 0.00
5.82	5.81	-0.01	17.46	17.46	± 0.00
11.64	11.62	-0.02	23.28	23.27	-0.01
11.64	11.65	+0.01	23.28	23.30	+0.02

Results

Quantitative precipitation of palladium with PBT occurred in the range of acidity from 1.6(N) to 0.08 (N) with respect to hydrochloric acid, and when the supernatant liquid contained about 0.015% (W/V) of the reagent in excess. Palladium was determined in presence of foreign ions (Table 2).

Precision and accuracy: When this procedure was applied to the determination of 5.82 mg of palladium the error did not exceed 0.03 mg. The relative standard deviation and relative mean error were found to be 0.13% and 0.24% respectively at 5 mg level (10 determinations).

Spectrophotometric Determination of Palladium :

Procedure: A known amount of palladium solution containing 100-120 μ g of the metal was introduced in a 100-ml separatory funnel, adjusted to pH 1.5-4.5, 2-3 ml of 0.01(M) ethanolic solution of PBT was added and mixed thoroughly. The mixture was allowed to stand for 5 minutes, 5 ml of ethanol added and the brown complex was extracted 2-3 times with 5-ml portions of chloroform. The extracts were collected in a 25 ml volumetric flask, diluted to the mark with chloroform and the absorbance was measured at 350 nm against appropriate reagent blank, prepared under similar conditions.

Results and Discussion

The absorbance curves of the extracts of the palladium-PBT complex in chloroform ethanol mixture, containing varying amounts of the metal are shown in Fig 1. The curves show maximum absorbance at 346 nm. The reagent has practically no absorption at and above 330 nm.

Fig. 1. Absorbance Curves of Palladium-N- α -Pyridyl-N'-Benzoyl Thiourea Complex in Chloroform-Ethanol Mixture. [Pd] : [⊙]=2.36 μ g/ml, [Δ]=4.72 μ g/ml, [●]=5.9 μ g/ml.

Quantitative extraction of palladium with PBT was possible when the pH of the aqueous layer was maintained between 1.4 and 4.6. The palladium complex was completely extracted in chloroform and in isobutylmethyl ketone in presence of a few ml of ethanol. In other solvents like benzene, nitrobenzene and carbon tetrachloride the complex was only partially extracted.

The palladium -N- α -pyridyl-N'-benzoyl thiourea system followed Beer's law at 350 nm over the range of concentration of the metal from 1.18 μ g/ml to 9.44 μ g/ml.

The empirical formula of the Pd-PBT complex was determined by the mole ratio method of Mayer and Ayres¹¹. The mole ratio curve showed that the stable complex is formed between palladium and the reagent in the molar ratio 1 : 1. The results were verified by the slope ratio method.

Effect of diverse ions: In determining the effect of base metal ions, a known amount of palladium solution was mixed with the desired amount the foreign ion and the pH was adjusted to 3.5-4.0. To avoid hydrolysis or interference of the ions, a suitable masking agent like EDTA or tartrate ions was added. Palladium was then spectrophotometrically determined with PBT by the above mentioned procedure.

Since the noble metals such as platinum (II and IV), ruthenium (III), gold(III) rhodium(III) do not form any complex with PBT at room temperature at pH 2.0, they produced no interference in the spectrophotometric determination of palladium with PBT. The interference of osmium(VI) was avoided by prior reduction of the metal ion with sulphur dioxide. The

tolerance limits (i. e. concentration of diverse ions causing an error less than $\pm 2\%$ in the transmittance value) are recorded in Table-3.

TABLE—2 GRAVIMETRIC OF DETERMINATION OF PALLADIUM WITH PBT IN PRESENCE OF DIVERSE IONS.

Palladium taken = 11.82 mg.

Diverse ion added mg.	Palladium found mg.	Diverse ion added mg.	Palladium found mg.
Co ²⁺ (300)	11.80	Hg ²⁺ (50)	11.85
Ni ²⁺ (500)	11.80	Cu ²⁺ (400)	11.85
Mn ²⁺ (300)	11.82	Mo ⁶⁺ (500)	11.85
Cr ³⁺ (500)	11.82	WO ₄ ²⁻ (500)	11.82
Fe ³⁺ (500)a	11.82	UO ₂ ²⁺ (500)	11.80
Al ³⁺ (500)	11.80	Th ⁴⁺ (500)	11.82
Ga ³⁺ (150)	11.85	Au ³⁺ (44.0)	11.82
In ³⁺ (150)	11.80	Ru ³⁺ (35.6)	11.85
Tl ³⁺ (150)	11.85	Rh ³⁺ (26.5)	11.80
Zn ²⁺ (500)	11.82	Os ⁶⁺ (31.2)	11.82
Cd ²⁺ (250)	11.80	Ir ³⁺ (32.4)	11.82

a=In presence of phosphoric acid.

TABLE—3 EFFECT OF DIVERSE IONS IN THE SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC DETERMINATION OF PALLADIUM WITH PBT.

Palladium taken = 118.2 μ g.

Diverse ion	Amount tolerated μ g.	Diverse ion	Amount tolerated μ g.
Co ²⁺	2500a	Pb ²⁺	1000a
Ni ²⁺	2000b	La ³⁺	1000a
Mn ²⁺	2500a	Mo ⁶⁺	2000a
Al ³⁺	1500a	WO ₄ ²⁻	2000a
Ga ³⁺	500a	UO ₂ ²⁺	1500a
In ³⁺	500a	Th ⁴⁺	1500a
Tl ³⁺	1000a	Au ³⁺	400b
Zn ²⁺	2000a	Ru ³⁺	200
Cd ²⁺	1000a	Rh ³⁺	300
Hg ²⁺	500b	Os ⁶⁺	312
Fe ³⁺	2000b	Ir ³⁺	320
Cu ²⁺	2000b	Pt ⁴⁺	200

a=In presence of tartrate
b=In presence of EDTA

Molar absorptivity, Sensitivity, Precision and Accuracy : The molar absorptivity of the palladium-PBT complex, the sensitivity of the colour reaction, the relative mean error and the coefficient of variation for the determination of palladium with PBT were found to be 1.05×10^4 L. mole⁻¹, cm⁻¹, 0.01 μ g cm⁻², 0.28% and 0.68% respectively.

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